

Development and Optimization of an Efficient In Vitro Regeneration Protocol for *Hemidesmus indicus* (L.) R. Br.

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Abstract: *Hemidesmus indicus* (L.) R. Br., commonly known as Indian sarsaparilla (*Anantmool*), is a medicinally important plant widely distributed across various regions of India. The species holds a prominent place in traditional Indian systems of medicine due to its broad spectrum of therapeutic properties. Previous studies have reported its aromatic, antimicrobial, anticancer, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, and antidiarrheal activities, along with significant antioxidant and hepatoprotective potential. Considering the medicinal importance and the presence of valuable phenolic compounds, the present study focuses on the development of an efficient in vitro tissue culture protocol for *H. indicus*. Various explants were cultured under controlled laboratory conditions using different concentrations of plant growth regulators in both solid and liquid culture media to induce multiple shoot and root formation. The results demonstrated a marked enhancement in shoot proliferation and root induction when appropriate combinations of growth hormones, nutrients, and culture media were employed. The optimized protocol provides a reliable method for rapid propagation and conservation of this valuable medicinal plant.

Keywords: *Hemidesmus indicus*, tissue culture, plant growth regulators, culture medium.

I. INTRODUCTION

Hemidesmus indicus (L.) R. Br. is a perennial twining shrub belonging to the family **Periplocaceae** (formerly Asclepiadaceae), commonly known as **Indian sarsaparilla** or *Anantmool*. In India, the species is widely distributed across most regions, extending from the upper Gangetic plains eastward to Assam and occurring throughout central, western, and southern parts of the country (1-2). Beyond India, its natural distribution includes Sri Lanka and the Moluccas (3-5). The plant occupies a significant position in traditional Indian systems of medicine, and its extracted plant materials are extensively utilized in the preparation of Ayurvedic, Unani, and Homeopathic formulations.

H. indicus is traditionally employed in the treatment of various ailments such as inflammatory conditions, fever, rheumatism, leprosy, and liver disorders (6). The roots possess a wide range of pharmacological properties, including aromatic, antimicrobial, anticancer, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, antipyretic, and antidiarrheal activities (7), along with notable antioxidant and hepatoprotective effects (8-9). Additionally, the roots are used as an adjunct therapy in the treatment of snakebite and scorpion sting (10-11). Owing to its extensive medicinal applications, *Anantmool* holds a prestigious place across all traditional medical systems in India (12). However, indiscriminate harvesting from natural habitats has resulted in severe depletion of wild populations, rendering the species increasingly rare due to overexploitation (13). Ethnic communities traditionally administer the roots internally for conditions such as premature greying of hair, jaundice, and various eye-related disorders.

Morphologically, the roots are long, rigid, cylindrical, and sparsely branched, comprising a lignified central core surrounded by a brownish corky bark marked with furrows and annular cracks. The stems and branches are elongated, narrow, and twine in an anticlockwise direction (14-15). They are profusely laticiferous, woody, and exhibit a deep purple to purplish-brown coloration, with slightly ridged surfaces at the nodes (16-19). Leaves are simple, petiolate,

exstipulate, opposite, and entire, with acute to obtuse apices. They are dark green on the upper surface and comparatively paler, occasionally pubescent, on the lower surface. Basal leaves are linear to lanceolate in shape (15). The flowers are small, axillary, and arranged in sessile racemes, greenish-yellow to greenish-purple externally and dull yellow to light purplish internally, accompanied by imbricate, scale-like bracts. The fruit consists of two long, slender, spreading follicles, while the seeds are numerous, flat, oblong, and bear a tuft of silky white hairs (20-22). Anatomically, transverse sections of the fresh root are circular with a fairly regular outline, containing a slightly porous woody strand at the center (23). The cork region comprises 3–15 layers of thick-walled, reddish-brown cells, followed by 2–3 layers of colorless phellogen and 1–2 layers of narrow, thin-walled phelloderm cells. Beneath this, 2–3 layers of thick-walled polygonal parenchymatous cells containing starch grains and calcium oxalate crystals are observed (24-25). The cortex is broad and composed of thin-walled, tangentially elongated cells rich in simple and compound starch grains and calcium oxalate prisms. The phloem is narrow and consists of sieve tubes, phloem parenchyma, companion cells, and uniseriate medullary rays (2,4,26). The cambium is distinct and narrow. The xylem contains scattered vessels with pitted walls, tracheids, thick-walled fibers, and uniseriate medullary rays (27).

II. MATERIAL AND METHODS

Healthy plants were collected from Sinhagad Fort, Pune, Maharashtra, located at 18°21'49.12" N latitude and 73°45'17.99" E longitude. The collected specimens were transported to the laboratory for further experimental procedures (28-29).

Preparation and Surface Sterilization of Explants: The collected plant material was initially washed thoroughly under running tap water with the addition of Tween-20 to remove surface contaminants (30). Stem nodal segments measuring 2–3 cm were excised and washed in running tap water for 30 minutes. The explants were subsequently treated with 1% (w/v) antifungal solution for 30 minutes under continuous shaking, followed by three washes with sterile autoclaved distilled water. Surface sterilization was carried out by treating the explants with mercuric chloride (HgCl₂) for 5–6 minutes, followed by a brief immersion in 70% ethanol for 15–20 seconds. The explants were then rinsed five times with sterile distilled water. All sterilization procedures were performed under aseptic conditions in a laminar air flow cabinet. The sterilized explants were subsequently inoculated onto the culture medium (31-34).

Preparation of Murashige and Skoog (MS) Medium: Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium was prepared using standard protocols. For full-strength MS medium, 3% sucrose (30 g L⁻¹) and 0.8% agar (8 g L⁻¹) were incorporated. The medium consisted of 50 ml macro-nutrient stock, 5 ml micro-nutrient stock, 1 ml organic supplement, and 5 ml iron (Fe) stock, with the final volume adjusted to 1000 ml using distilled water. The pH of the medium was adjusted to 5.8 prior to autoclaving (35).

For half-strength MS (MS_{1/2}) medium, 25 ml macro-nutrient stock, 2.5 ml micro-nutrient stock, 0.5 ml organic supplement, and 2.5 ml Fe stock were used along with 1.5% sucrose (15 g L⁻¹) and 0.8% agar (4 g L⁻¹). The final volume was adjusted to 1000 ml, and the pH was maintained at 5.8.

Hormonal Treatments: Different concentrations of plant growth regulators (PGRs) were incorporated into both MS and MS_{1/2} media to study their effects on shoot proliferation and root induction (36-37).

Inoculation Procedure: Under aseptic conditions in a laminar air flow cabinet, surface-sterilized explants of 2–3 cm length were placed on sterile Petri plates. Both ends of the explants were trimmed using a sterile surgical blade, and the explants were inoculated onto autoclaved slanted culture tubes containing the prepared medium (38-39).

Root Culture: Well-developed roots obtained from subcultured plantlets, measuring 1–1.5 cm, were excised and thoroughly washed to remove adhering solid medium. Three to four root segments were transferred to 500 ml conical flasks containing 50 ml of liquid MS_{1/2} medium supplemented with varying concentrations of plant growth regulators, along with a control (40). The cultures were maintained under dark conditions on a rotary shaker at 70 rpm.

Anatomical Studies: Comparative anatomical analyses were performed on *in vivo* and *in vitro* raised plants. Samples included the second leaf, stem segment from the second nodal region, and newly formed root tips (7,9,12). Transverse sections of leaf, stem, and root tissues were prepared and stained with safranin and light green. The stained sections

were mounted in 50% glycerin for microscopic examination. Observations focused on the presence and density of leaf and stem trichomes, with counts recorded across 20 microscopic fields for both in vivo and in vitro samples (25).

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Statistically analysis of rooting and shooting observation

Sr. No	Medium +PGR mg/lit	Number of Replicates for observation	Sum of length of roots in cm	Number of Roots/replicate	Sum of length of shoots in cm	Tot no. of shoots/replicate
1	MS CON	20	0.912.9±0.21	0.970±1.21	2.514±2.80	1.025±0.254
2	MS +KN	60	1.10548±0.253	2.101±1.53	5.575 ±3.1319	1.75 ±0.8660
3	MS _{1/2} CON	40	0.8±05.1072	1.5±2.010	1.9±2.45	1.3±2.234
4	MS _{1/2} +IBA 1.0	100	1.489±0.9222	2±1.1094	3.1875±2.7861	0.75 ±0.1670
5	MS _{1/2} +IBA 1.5	100	2.009±1.4171	2.0153±1.260	2.96153±1.5380	2.30 ±0.5201
6	MS _{1/2} +IBA 2.0	100	1.139±0.81135	3.13636±1.5787	3.8421±2.193	3.01 ±2.3012
7	MS _{1/2} +IBA 2.5	100	1.12246±0.8275	2.66667±1.4505	3.2021±1.6235	2.61±1.2540

Graphical representation of rooting and shooting

Fresh mass of root in different IBA concentration

Comparison of number of trichomes *in vivo* and *in vitro*:-

No. of Field	Number of <i>In vivo</i> trichomes	No. of Field	Number of <i>In vivo</i> trichomes	No. of Field	Number of <i>In vivo</i> trichomes	No. of Field	Number of <i>In vivo</i> trichomes
1	11	1	7	11	8	11	5
2	12	2	8	12	10	12	6
3	12	3	9	13	9	13	5
4	14	4	6	14	10	14	6
5	9	5	4	15	10	15	5
6	9	6	7	16	8	16	7
7	10	7	4	17	7	17	6
8	9	8	5	18	10	18	5
9	6	9	9	19	12	19	6
10	12	10	5	20	8	20	6
				Tot.	196		121
				Mean	9.8		6.05

***In vivo* and *in vitro* anatomical observation**

Shoot, Root culture observation and Hardening of plant

IV. CONCLUSION

In vitro shoot multiplication exhibited a maximum response on Murashige and Skoog (MS) medium supplemented with kinetin and NAA, where a higher mean number of shoots per explant was recorded. However, the mean shoot length was significantly greater on half-strength MS ($MS_{1/2}$) medium supplemented with IBA at 2.0 mg L^{-1} . These observations are in agreement with the findings reported by Sreekumar and Seeni (1998). Root induction studies revealed that $MS_{1/2}$ medium supplemented with IBA at 1.5 mg L^{-1} resulted in the highest rooting response and maximum number of roots per explant. Furthermore, root proliferation in liquid culture was most pronounced on $MS_{1/2}$ medium containing IBA at 2.0 mg L^{-1} , which showed a significant increase in fresh root biomass. Comparative anatomical analysis of in vivo and in vitro raised plantlets indicated a noticeably higher density of trichomes in in vitro cultured plants compared to those grown under natural conditions.

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